

INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES APPLIED IN EDUCATION: COMMUNICATION AND DISTANCE EDUCATION

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Abstract

Current Education seeks the use of information and communication technologies in education. The objective of this work is to analyze how the use of these technologies can influence and improve communication in face-to-face and distance education. The conditions, limits and possibilities of the digital media in the classes were analyzed. It was concluded that Education has greater interactivity and a strong presence of digital media so that knowledge can be constructed collectively.

Keywords: Education. Distance education. ICTs. Communication.

Introduction

This article will address how information and communication technologies (ICTs) are used in Education and how communication is involved in the educational sphere, whether in person or at a distance. We live in times of the information society, with wide use of Web 2.0 for various purposes, in addition to the massive presence of cyberspace in almost everything that is necessary.

This cyberspace, according to Lévy (2000) is defined as:

[...] cyberspace (which I will also call “network”) is the new means of communication that arises from the worldwide interconnection of computers. The term specifies not only the material infrastructure of digital communication, but also the oceanic universe of information it houses, as well as the human beings who navigate and feed this universe (LÉVY, 2000).

In this context, Education undergoes changes that accompany technological innovations, such as Distance Learning, access to virtual libraries, communication of students

and teachers through virtual social networks, use of applications, e-books , smartphones , among others in the process of teaching-learning.

Thus, with a scenario in which information arrives at an ever-faster speed and with Education and its members being involved in this update, it is necessary to make adaptations in the way of teaching and learning in the face of the information society and cyberspace. .

Theoretical Reference

2.1. The Use of Information and Communication Technologies in Education

In the “information society” we live in, it is based on information and knowledge, which is different from the old “industrial society” which was based on production and capital. Thus, according to Silveira (2019), we live in a society in which information comes all the time with something new and always updated at high speed. Technologies are present in all environments, including Education.

The Internet has several resources to be used in the school environment through Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), such as virtual learning environments such as Moodle. In addition, resources such as virtual social networks, educational objects, educational repositories, among many other means that can be used at different levels of education: elementary, secondary and higher.

According to Lévy (1995), the internet appears in the academic scenario for research purposes and later for society as a whole; after that its popularization occurs, having at that moment the end of Web 1.0 and the beginning of Web 2.0. Web 2.0 introduces several features such as chat rooms, email, forums and virtual social networks such as Whatsapp , Facebook , Twitter , Hangouts , among others that promote interaction between people anywhere , regardless of distance.

With the emergence of the Internet, in its Web 1.0 phase and its subsequent development to the Web 2.0 phase, where we can make purchases and sales, access banking services, among other services, it also provided the improvement and evolution of Education. From this perspective, it made it possible for distance education to advance with quality, so that students can study and communicate with colleagues and professors from several kilometers away, with the possibility of taking open, undergraduate and graduate courses.

Today, ICTs are present in most stages of teaching and learning. This presence of ICTs takes place in internet research, in software, in the use of social networks, in the sharing of documents in the cloud, in the use of hypermedia and multimedia, among other tools. Distance learning is a striking example of this new Education, although there is still prejudice from people who doubt this teaching instrument, which will occupy even more space in the future.

We live in a transition phase of distance education. Distance education is seen as a teaching-learning process that uses different forms of technology and its tools so that the main objective is achieved. Resources such as wikis, discussion forums, web conferences, submission of forms and activities are used (MORAN, 2017). In this type of education, the teacher is not physically seen by the student; which is not to say that he is not there. On the

contrary, the student has the virtual presence of the educator, demanding discipline from the student, which is the most important element for learning to take place.

Aiming at the success of this learning, the information and knowledge acquired in a collective and collaborative way can also be carried out with the collaboration of everyone involved. This type of action, as stated by Da Silva Zago and Batista (2009), when carried out on the Internet, can lead to forms of coordinated collective action, in search of common goals, based on common interests, and which demand an active and conscious role for part of individuals in order to respond effectively to media messages.

In this context mentioned above, forms of collective action emerge in cyberspace, which depend on the common effort of different social actors to achieve the expected effect. These forms of action often draw on the potential of the web's network structure.

This teaching-learning process, as Medeiros et al (2012), in their analysis and experiences with students and tutors using the resources of Moodle reports:

The network created establishes a differentiated didactic relationship between the participants (students and tutors), marked by the commitment to individual and collective activities, generating responsibility for the other and for the training process itself. An example of this is the effective participation of students, both to develop group work and to exchange readings and comments on the memorials (MEDEIROS et al, 2012, p. 51).

The teacher becomes a mediator and encourager by teaching the student the intended content and the student has the possibility to study at any time and in any location. Since some courses the student has the ability to study alone and at other times with the mediation of his teacher.

In this context of full technological evolution, Moran (2017) explains that distance education can be done at all levels of regular education. It is more suitable for adult education, especially for those who already have a consolidated experience of individual learning and research, such as in graduate and undergraduate education.

The great importance of using information and communication technologies, such as Moodle in the classroom (virtual and in-person) is the type of knowledge that is built, since learning takes place collectively, with student interaction and teacher participation. This knowledge, carried out with the participation of everyone and with the possibility of viewing the history of everything that happened, makes it a dynamic and integrative learning process (SILVEIRA, 2019).

Information and communication technologies enable students to learn using a tool that is in constant use by them. That way, they can learn in a lighter and more fun way. Through ICTs, students can create knowledge through opinions, suggestions, adding to what was written by another, contributing to the increase of knowledge.

For the teacher, there are also advantages in using ICTs, as they can monitor comments, posts, files, among others. Finally, he has the power to monitor, mediate, and participate in the construction of learning. Thus, all the experiences of students and teachers can be shared and

accessed at any time in the school environment or outside it. All these teaching and learning experiences with different possibilities for use at all levels of education.

2.2. Communication and Distance Education

The physical structure of the school and the university are not currently the only places to seek knowledge and academic training. Education became multiple and decentralized. The teacher's figure is still the main one for the contents to be passed on to the students. However, the teacher is no longer seen as the holder of knowledge and truth. Today, students bring information from the web, which is accessed all the time, and the teacher becomes the mediator of all student knowledge.

Santos and Weber (2013) report that, from the end of the 20th century, the intensification and scope of technological advances related to computing have produced transformations in various social media, both in-person and virtual. One of the technologies that provided the advancement and current scope of distance learning is the Internet, which allows the exchange of information between participants quickly and efficiently.

Technology cannot be excluded from the pedagogical and communicative model of schools. In this case, technology must be an apparatus for improving, transforming and modernizing teaching, not for transforming methodological structures and learning practices. Given this scenario, transactional distance can be a problem linked to communication in education.

According to Baccega (2009), transactional distance is the perception of the real distance between the educator and the learner, being considered the biggest challenge of any and all Distance Education (EaD) institution. The smaller this perception, the more effective the DL method adopted will be. The transactional distance is shortened when the system uses resources that promote interactivity between the student and the teacher.

Distance education demonstrates that resources such as interactive video classes, associated with good teaching material, are the ones that most reduce the transactional distance between the educator and the student. The availability of other synchronous and asynchronous communication resources such as chat, discussion forum, among others, is also a strong ally in this cognitive process.

The transactional distance can still be reduced when education systems also associate synchronous and asynchronous resources in the right measure and, preferably, dosed according to the cognitive profile of each student. In this context, the importance of communication in Education emerges.

Communication is a social fact, one of the elements that constitute the educational process, which leads to the realization of the educational process. Communication presents a set of procedures for connecting people, it is a transversal axis in educational practice between teachers and students.

Education and communication become necessary to adapt the service to the needs of teachers and students. Citelli (2010) reports that the growth in the participation of information

and communication technologies (ICTs) in the social space reinforces this concern, as the means of communication also occupy school spaces.

Communication in distance education involves a series of issues that deserve attention so that a continuous dialogue takes place between all actors in the teaching and learning process. The ultimate goal should be student learning through a pedagogical mediation that takes account of the paradigm shifts that online education brings (BACCEGA, 2009).

According to Setton (2010), dialogism is already a reality in several teaching materials for classroom teaching, however when it comes to EaD, this dialogic character is essential, as it aims to bring those who are physically distant. It is as if the teacher and author, physically distant from the students, could be present, involved in the construction of a conversational style.

The learning process occurs due to different factors that involve the teacher, the student, the school environment, the methodologies and tools used in this process. The advancement of technology provides the emergence of new tools and services available on the Internet. These tools and services can be used educationally and it is useful to be constantly updated on these new possibilities.

Children and young people have easy contact with these new tools and it is appropriate that these resources are also present during their educational activities. Often, it is necessary to combine more than one tool available on the Internet in order to attract students' attention and complement their knowledge.

The teacher, as knowledgeable about the content of their discipline, must be able to develop this activity of writing materials for the distance modality, taking into account current pedagogical concepts, knowledge of their target audience, the possibilities of intersection with the media and language issues.

In addition to the different modes of communication, it is necessary to create conditions for the development of media skills that favor communication that promotes effective interaction between students and professors on the Web. interaction, otherwise, one may be using the most advanced technology to do the obvious or the traditional (SETTON, 2010).

Just because the use of information and communication technologies are present in everyday education, both in face-to-face and distance learning, it is already an important step and seen as transformative. In the case of EaD, what imposes conditions, limits and possibilities are the digital media, however, at the same time, the same medium seen, at first as limiting, also enhances other forms of pedagogical work.

According to Kellner (2001), for the new communication tools to really be effective in opening new arenas in the exchange of ideas and in the construction of meanings, it is necessary that teachers effectively incorporate these tools within their pedagogical repertoire. This entire process should not be seen in an imposing way, but an authentic interaction that needs reflection for its proper and effective use.

Discussions

The development of information and communication technologies generate new work rhythms, new environments, new instruments, new languages or forms of expression. Thus, it becomes necessary to consider the media as objects of study, with their ethical and aesthetic aspects, and as pedagogical and didactic tools. This scenario of pedagogical action in online environments reveals that it is necessary to stop being mere spectators and start having a profile of “active participants”.

To improve their teaching activity, the educator can use distance learning resources in their classes, even if they are exclusively on-site. In distance learning, the student performs most of their learning through teaching materials prepared by the teacher and also through traditional or innovative teaching materials selected by the teacher. Examples of these teaching materials are books (e-books), handouts and video lessons.

Communication within the educational sphere demonstrates the transition from an educational system to a society of continuous education and learning, with no age for knowledge, no single space for sharing knowledge. Students, researchers and professionals, communicators and educators, must always remain interested in understanding the thinking of the new model of communication and education.

Conclusions

The contemporary education in which we are living provides a teaching and learning model that is different from traditional means. The information society seeks greater interactivity, collectively built knowledge and a strong presence of digital media, including the use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in teaching.

Thus, teaching and learning in the virtual environment comprises some similarities with the traditional way, such as the interaction between students and teacher, the need for reflection, analysis and interpretation of texts, information and what is taught. It is also necessary to emphasize that virtual education can be carried out at different levels of education, both primary, secondary and higher.

However, what changes is the way to obtain knowledge, since classrooms are no longer necessarily physical, much less also with the physical presence of the teacher in that environment. Schools and universities are now present 24 hours a day and with access available to the student whenever he has it. All this using the internet.

The continuing education of teachers is necessary so that they can guide students about the proper use of Web tools, virtual social networks, applications and software, so that, in addition to the pursuit of citizenship education, they also seek digital inclusion.

Furthermore, teachers should seek to plan activities to put themselves in pedagogical practice in cyberspace. To carry out activities including technological resources, an organization is needed in order to profitably explore the available resources, allowing learning to be shared with the objectives of disseminating educational information and boosting the participation of students and teachers in digital culture in the context of education.

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